

Рисунок 4. Разница температуры между фактической и полученный с модели

Анализ температурных полей марта 2024 года для региона Аральского моря подтверждает тенденцию к потеплению климата и усилению его континентальности. Наблюдаемые изменения согласуются с глобальными климатическими трендами, но проявляются с большей амплитудой в условиях антропогенно трансформированного ландшафта бывшего морского дна. Полученные данные свидетельствуют о:

Ускорении сезонных переходов (более раннее наступление весны);

Увеличении термической контрастности как в суточном, так и в пространственном аспектах;

Формировании специфического микроклимата в районе регрессировавшего Аральского моря.

Использованной литературы

1. Описание модели Advanced ResearchWRF версии 4 Уильям К. Скамарок Джозеф, июль 2021г. (<https://www.ecampmany.com/docs/cheatsheets/WRF.pdf>).
2. ВОЗМОЖНОЕ БУДУЩЕЕ АРАЛЬСКОГО МОРЯ И ЕГО ФАУНЫ Филип Миклин, 2016г. (<https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/vozmozhnoe-buduschee-aralskogo-morya-i-ego-fauny>).
3. Катастрофа Аральского моря, Филип Миклин 2007г. (https://www.researchgate.net/publication/228348689_The_Aral_Sea_disaster).
4. Тажиниязов Ниязбек Айбосин Ули, РГГМУ, студент 2-го курса магистратуры, niyazbek.tazhiniyazov@bk.ru
5. Анискина Ольга Георгиевна, РГГМУ, заведующая кафедры метеорологического факультета, olga.aniskina@mail.ru

Yarashev D.¹, Umirzakov G.^{1,2}, Gafurov A.³

Hydrometeorological Research Institute, Tashkent, Uzbekistan, ²Justus Liebig University Giessen, Germany, ³GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences, Potsdam, Germany,

E-mail: d.yarashev.hmri@uz

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20237389>

ASSESSMENT OF ERA5-LAND SNOW DEPTH DATA BASED ON MOUNTAIN METEOROLOGICAL STATIONS IN UZBEKISTAN

Abstract: Seasonal snow cover plays an important role in river runoff formation and water resources in the mountainous regions of Central Asia. This study evaluates ERA5-Land snow depth data using long-term ground-based observations from mountain meteorological stations in Uzbekistan during 1996–2025. Statistical validation using R, RMSE, MAE, Bias, and NSE showed good agreement at several stations, while significant overestimation was observed at some high mountain stations. The results indicate that ERA5-Land has strong potential for snow monitoring in mountainous regions with limited observations.

Keywords: ERA5-Land, snow depth, reanalysis, mountain hydrology, meteorological stations, snow monitoring, statistical validation

Seasonal snow cover is one of the main components of mountain hydrological systems and plays an important role in river runoff formation in Central Asia. Snow accumulation during winter and subsequent snowmelt during spring and summer significantly influence regional water resources, irrigation systems, and hydropower production [1]. Therefore, reliable monitoring of snow cover dynamics is essential for hydrological forecasting and climate-related studies.

Ground-based snow observations in mountainous regions are often spatially limited because meteorological stations are sparse and unevenly distributed, especially in high mountain areas. In such conditions, atmospheric and land-surface reanalysis datasets provide an important alternative source of snow information. ERA5-Land is a modern high-resolution global land reanalysis dataset that includes snow depth and other land-surface variables and is widely used in hydrological and climate studies [2].

Despite the increasing use of ERA5-Land data, its performance in the mountainous regions of Central Asia remains insufficiently studied. Complex terrain and strong spatial variability of snowfall may lead to uncertainties in snow depth representation within reanalysis products. Therefore, validation of ERA5-Land snow depth data using long-term ground-based observations is necessary for assessing its applicability in regional snow monitoring and hydrological research.

The main objective of this study is to evaluate ERA5-Land snow depth data using long-term observations from mountain meteorological stations in Uzbekistan and assess its potential for snow monitoring in observation-scarce mountainous regions.

Reliable information about snow cover conditions is critically important for water resource management and hydrological forecasting in Central Asia. Mountain snow accumulation serves as a major source of river runoff in the region, particularly during spring and summer periods [1]. However, observational snow data in mountainous regions of Uzbekistan remain limited because meteorological stations are sparse and unevenly distributed.

In recent years, reanalysis datasets have become widely used for regional hydrological and climate studies due to their continuous spatial and temporal coverage. Among them, ERA5-Land provides high-resolution snow depth information and has significant potential for snow monitoring applications [2]. Nevertheless, uncertainties associated with complex mountain terrain may affect the accuracy of reanalysis snow products.

Therefore, evaluation of ERA5-Land snow depth data using long-term ground-based observations is scientifically and practically important for determining its applicability in mountainous regions of Uzbekistan.

The study was conducted in the mountainous regions of Uzbekistan located within the western Tien Shan and Pamir-Alay mountain systems (Figure 1). These mountain regions are characterized by complex topography, large elevation gradients, and seasonal snow accumulation during winter months. Snow cover in these areas plays an important role in river runoff formation and regional water resources of Central Asia [1].

Long-term ground-based snow depth observations from seven meteorological stations were used in this study. The selected stations are located at elevations ranging from 1258 to 2161 m above sea level, which allows evaluation of ERA5-Land performance under different topographic conditions. The stations include Chimgan, Dukant, Kul, Minchukur, Oygaing, Pskem, and Qamchiq.

The study area has a continental climate with cold winters and relatively warm summers. Seasonal snow accumulation generally occurs from November to April, while snowmelt processes dominate during spring months. Due to the sparse distribution of meteorological stations in mountainous regions, reanalysis datasets such as ERA5-Land are increasingly used for regional snow monitoring and hydrological studies [2].

In this study, long-term ground-based snow depth observations from seven mountain meteorological stations located in the mountainous regions of Uzbekistan were used. Daily snow depth data covering the period 1996–2025 were collected from 7 hydrometeorological observation stations situated at different elevations.

Figure 1. Location of meteorological stations

ERA5-Land snow depth data were used as the reanalysis dataset for comparison with ground observations. ERA5-Land is a global land-surface reanalysis product developed by the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts and provides atmospheric and land-surface variables with high spatial and temporal resolution [2]. The dataset has a spatial resolution of $0.1^\circ \times 0.1^\circ$ and hourly temporal resolution. Snow depth values corresponding to the nearest ERA5-Land grid cells for each meteorological station were extracted and converted into daily values for analysis.

The performance of ERA5-Land snow depth data was evaluated using several statistical indicators, including correlation coefficient (R), root mean square error (RMSE), mean absolute error (MAE), Bias, and Nash–Sutcliffe efficiency (NSE). Correlation coefficient was used to assess the temporal agreement between observed and reanalysis data, while RMSE and MAE were applied to quantify the magnitude of errors. Bias was used to determine systematic overestimation or underestimation of snow depth by ERA5-Land, and NSE was used to evaluate overall model performance.

In addition, seasonal analysis and snow occurrence validation were conducted to assess the capability of ERA5-Land to reproduce seasonal snow dynamics and snow presence conditions in mountainous regions.

Table 1. Statistical validation results between ground-based observations and ERA5-Land snow depth data

Station	R	R2	MAE	RMSE	Bias	NSE
Minchuqur	0.94	0.89	5.9	12.25	4.41	0.792
Kul	0.67	0.45	44.35	69.52	44.33	-9.962
Qamchiq	0.91	0.83	8.65	16.93	6.57	0.749
Dukant	0.96	0.92	5.94	12.57	-3.61	0.887
Chimyon	0.90	0.80	16.74	29.66	16.54	-0.019
Oygain	0.85	0.72	42.86	62.31	42.58	-0.336
Piskem	0.69	0.47	52.18	79.58	52.18	-8.969

Scatter plot analysis further demonstrated the differences in ERA5-Land performance among the studied stations (Figure 2). At Dukant, Minchuqur, and Qamchiq stations, most points were concentrated near the 1:1 reference line, indicating strong agreement between observed and ERA5-

Land snow depth values. Dukant station showed the best overall performance with the highest coefficient of determination ($R^2 = 0.922$) and relatively small bias (-3.61 cm), suggesting that ERA5-Land reproduced both low and high snow depth conditions reasonably well.

Figure 2. Scatter plots showing the relationship between ground-based observations and ERA5-Land snow depth data at selected meteorological stations

Similarly, Minchuqur and Qamchiq stations exhibited relatively strong linear relationships between observed and modeled snow depth values, with R^2 values of 0.891 and 0.834, respectively. Although ERA5-Land slightly overestimated snow depth at these stations, the overall temporal consistency remained high.

In contrast, scatter plots for Kul, Oygain, and Piskem stations revealed substantial deviations from the 1:1 line. ERA5-Land systematically overestimated snow depth at these stations, particularly during moderate and high snow conditions. This effect was especially pronounced at Piskem and Oygain stations, where Bias values exceeded 40–50 cm. The large spread of points and lower R^2 values indicate increased uncertainty of ERA5-Land snow representation in complex mountainous terrain.

Overall, the scatter plot analysis confirms that ERA5-Land reproduces snow depth dynamics more accurately at some stations while exhibiting considerable overestimation in several high mountain regions. These results highlight the influence of local topographic and climatic conditions on reanalysis snow depth performance.

The statistical validation results demonstrated considerable spatial variability in ERA5-Land snow depth performance across the study area (Table 1). High agreement between ERA5-Land and observed snow depth was obtained at Dukant, Minchuqur, and Qamchiq stations, where correlation coefficients exceeded 0.90. The highest correlation was observed at Dukant station ($R = 0.96$), accompanied by relatively low RMSE and MAE values as well as a high NSE value (0.887), indicating good reproduction of snow depth dynamics by ERA5-Land.

Similarly, Minchuqur and Qamchiq stations also showed strong agreement between observed and reanalysis data, with NSE values of 0.792 and 0.749, respectively. These results indicate that ERA5-Land can successfully represent seasonal snow variability in some mountainous regions of Uzbekistan.

However, substantial differences were identified at several stations, particularly in higher mountain regions. Kul, Oygain, and Piskem stations exhibited relatively large RMSE, MAE, and Bias values, indicating considerable overestimation of snow depth by ERA5-Land. The highest RMSE value was observed at Piskem station (79.58 cm), while Bias values exceeded 40 cm at Kul, Oygain, and Piskem stations. In addition, negative NSE values at several stations suggest weak agreement between observed and modeled snow depth conditions.

The obtained results indicate that ERA5-Land performance strongly depends on local topographic and climatic conditions. While the dataset reproduces temporal snow dynamics relatively well at some stations, significant uncertainties remain in complex mountainous terrain where snow accumulation processes are highly variable. Nevertheless, the relatively high correlation coefficients obtained at most stations demonstrate the potential applicability of ERA5-Land data for regional-scale snow monitoring in observation-scarce mountainous regions.

This study evaluated ERA5-Land snow depth data using long-term ground-based observations from mountain meteorological stations in Uzbekistan during 1981–2025. The results showed that ERA5-Land reproduced snow depth dynamics reasonably well at Dukant, Minchuqur, and Qamchiq stations, where high correlation coefficients and relatively low errors were obtained. However, significant overestimation of snow depth was detected at several high mountain stations, particularly at Kul, Oygain, and Piskem. Seasonal analysis indicated that ERA5-Land performed better during winter snow accumulation periods than during spring snowmelt conditions. Overall, the obtained results demonstrate that ERA5-Land has strong potential for regional snow monitoring in observation-scarce mountainous regions, although uncertainties remain in complex high-altitude terrain.

References

1. Barnett, T.P., Adam, J.C., Lettenmaier, D.P. Potential impacts of a warming climate on water availability in snow-dominated regions // *Nature*, 2005, 438. – PP. 303–309. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature04141>
2. Muñoz-Sabater, J., Dutra, E., Agustí-Panareda, A., Albergel, C., Arduini, G., Balsamo, G., et al. ERA5-Land: a state-of-the-art global reanalysis dataset for land applications // *Earth System Science Data*, 2021, 13(9). – PP. 4349–4383. <https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-13-4349-2021>

Қуватов Д.Р., Юнусов Ф.Х.

Мирзо Улуғбек номидаги Ўзбекистон Миллий университети,
Тошкент, Ўзбекистон, E.mail: yunusov-g@mail.ru

**ҚАШҚАДАРЁ ВИЛОЯТИ СУҒОРИЛАДИГАН ЕРЛАРИНИ СУВ БИЛАН
ТАЪМИНЛАНИШ ҲОЛАТИНИ ГАТ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРИ ЁРДАМИДА БАҲОЛАШ**

Аннотация. Мақолада Қашқадарё воҳасининг суғориладиган ер майдонлари, уларнинг ҳудудий жойлашуви ва қишлоқ хўжалиги экинлари таркиби таҳлил қилинган. Тадқиқотда воҳадаги суғориладиган ерларнинг асосий қисми Амударё, Зарафшон ва Қашқадарё ҳавзалари сув ресурслари ҳисобига таъминланиши ёритилган. Шунингдек, туманлар кесимида пахта, галла ва бошқа қишлоқ хўжалиги экинларининг жойлашув хусусиятлари ҳамда уларнинг табиий-географик омиллар билан боғлиқлиги баҳоланган. Тадқиқот жараёнида ГИС технологиялари асосида 1:500 000 масштабда Қашқадарё вилоятининг суғориш ва сув билан таъминланганлик харитаси яратилган. Харитада суғориладиган майдонлар, сув манбалари, магистрал каналлар, коллекторлар, сув омборлари ҳамда уларнинг техник кўрсаткичлари акс эттирилган.

Калит сўзлар: дарё, сув сарфи, канал, ирригация, ГАТ, технология, экин майдони, сувнинг сарфланиши, сув ресурслари, сув таъминоти, баҳолаш.